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Overview of energy production potential in the wastewater sector

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Abstract

Most wastewater treatment plants are designed to meet certain effluent requirements without considering energy efficiency. However, this situation has changed in recent years, as both water and energy are critical elements. In most WWTPs, water quality is improved at the cost of consuming a large amount of energy. WWTPs are often ranked as the single largest energy consumers managed by a municipality. In a conventional WWTP, about 25-40% of operating costs can be attributed to energy consumption. Therefore, it is necessary to reduce energy consumption or improve energy independence. Over the last decade, energy self-sustaining wastewater treatment plants have been increasingly built and studied to reduce operating costs and energy consumption and to achieve carbon neutrality. The European Union has recognized wastewater as a resource for energy production since 2018. Facing such challenging situations, new solutions should rely on ways to improve energy recovery from wastewater (in the water line and in the sludge line) and minimize energy consumption. Energy can be recovered from wastewater in the form of biogas, biodiesel, hydrogen, electricity, and thermal energy. Hence, these new technologies with the potential for energy recovery and saving are the way to move towards the ultimate goal of energy-self-sustainable wastewater treatment.

Keywords: energy recovery, saving energy, wastewater treatment

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